

EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT TYPE ON MATRIX PRECIPITATION IN ALUMINIUM ALLOY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effect on precipitation behaviour of introducing, firstly, short alumina (Saffil) fibres and, secondly, TiB_2 particulates into an aluminium-copper alloy containing small amounts (< 0.5 wt.%) of magnesium and/or silver is described. Some fairly coarse intermetallic phases were present in all materials, mainly at grain boundaries, which were difficult to remove entirely by the prescribed solution treatment. Hardness tests showed that when either composite was aged at $140^\circ C.$, the time taken to reach the hardness maximum was significantly less than with the corresponding unreinforced metal. It was also found that the composite containing TiB_2 particulates gave a higher matrix peak hardness, an effect which is attributed to a combination of particulate and age-hardening precipitate. Transmission electron microscopy of samples in the peak-hardness condition showed that the unreinforced alloy contained a mixture of Ω and θ' precipitates lying on $\{111\}$ and $\{100\}$ planes of the aluminium lattice respectively, whereas only θ' phase was present in the composite materials.

Keywords: composite, aluminium, Saffil, boride dispersion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Whilst the reinforcement of aluminium alloys with unidirectional high strength ceramic fibres can significantly improve properties in the direction of reinforcement, benefits in the transverse direction are usually very limited [1]. Thus for optimum mechanical performance a matrix microstructure is required whereby both longitudinal and transverse properties are enhanced. A method by which this may be achieved involves using, as the matrix, a metal which can be strengthened via a precipitation-hardening reaction, as in alloys based upon aluminium-4% copper [2,3]. In such studies it has, however, been observed that precipitation processes may be changed in the presence of reinforcements and this has led to the proposal that the high dislocation densities created by stresses produced upon cooling the composite from the manufacturing temperature can affect the nucleation and growth of precipitate in a number of ways. The present work investigates for use as a composite matrix material an aluminium-copper alloy which contains small (< 0.5 wt.%) amounts of magnesium and silver, an alloy formulation which has commercial interest because of its high strength and good age-hardening response [4] as well as satisfactory casting characteristics [5]. The hardness response in this system has been shown to be associated with the formation of a precipitate, designated Ω , which appears as thin hexagonal platelets on $\{111\}$ planes of the aluminium lattice [6,7]. Further, it has been noted that precipitation of θ' phase on $\{100\}$ planes may occur in these alloys, the relative proportion of Ω and θ' precipitate which forms depending upon the specific and relative concentrations of magnesium and silver [4]. Thus when these alloys are used in a metal matrix composite (MMC) it might be expected that precipitation behaviour would be influenced also by the presence of precipitate nucleation sites such as the fibre-matrix interface or dislocations generated as a result of the large thermal

mismatch between matrix and reinforcement. This paper describes preliminary results on the development of strengthening precipitates in composites based upon an aluminium-copper alloy matrix containing two different types of reinforcement.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Three materials have been studied:

(a) unreinforced Al-4%Cu-0.3%Mg-0.5%Ag alloy supplied as sand-cast blocks,

(b) reinforced Al-4%Cu-0.3%Mg-0.5%Ag alloy containing ~10 vol.% short alumina ("Saffil") fibres 3 to 4µm diameter. This material was manufactured by squeeze casting, a process which involved infiltrating liquid metal under pressure (~20 MPa) into a preheated fibre preform. After extraction from the die, the outer regions of the cast material were removed to leave the fibre-reinforced central section.

(c) Reinforced Al-5%Cu-0.2%Mg alloy containing ~5vol.% TiB₂ particulates, 1-2µm in diameter. This material was fabricated by reaction casting (London and Scandinavian Metallurgical Co. Ltd).

All materials were given an initial homogenising treatment consisting of 6 hours at 500°C. followed by 42 hours at 525°C. The specimens were then cold water quenched and aged in air at 140°C. for times of up to ~ 500 hours.

Following metallographic preparation of the specimens, microhardness tests were performed on samples of each material using a LECO M-400 instrument fitted with a Vickers pyramid indenter and using a load of 25gf. Ten measurements were made on each sample and error bars representing 95% confidence limits are included in the plots of hardness versus ageing time.

Optical microscopy on polished sections was carried out using a Zeiss microscope. In addition, some specimens were examined in the scanning electron microscope (SEM) and these were usually coated with a thin layer of gold to avoid charging up of the surface during examination. Compositional analysis data were obtained using an energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS) attached to the SEM.

Thin sections (~200nm thick) were prepared from each material for transmission electron microscopy (TEM). This involved cutting a thin (< 1mm) slice of material and drilling from it a 3mm diameter disc. The disc was then dimpled on both sides and ion-beam thinned until perforation, using a liquid nitrogen cold stage to prevent heating of the specimen. Selected-area electron diffraction (SAD) patterns were taken and EDS data were obtained during TEM examination in order to provide supporting information. Finally, electron-probe microanalysis (EPMA) was carried out using wavelength-dispersive spectrometry (WDS) in order to obtain quantitative composition data.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Unreinforced alloy

Solution treatment (6 h. at 500°C. followed by 42 h. at 525°C.) was found to remove successfully the cored structure which characterised this alloy in the cast condition [5]. Much of the grain-boundary phase was also dissolved by the treatment but a significant amount (~5% by volume) still remained, see Figure 1. EPMA revealed that the residual particles contained ~63 wt.% aluminium, ~28 wt.% copper, 8 wt.% iron and 2 wt.% manganese. Intermetallics of similar composition, such as Cu₂FeAl₇, have previously been located in alloys of this formulation and found to be resistant

to the solution-treatment temperature [5].

A plot of hardness values versus ageing time at 140°C. is illustrated in Figure 2. The curve shows a small progressive increase in hardness over the first thirty hours, to reach a value of ~150 HV after a hundred hours or so. It is possible that the alloy had not reached peak hardness even after 500 hours at 140°C. There was found to be a small progressive increase in the amount of grain-boundary phase present with increase in ageing time.

A TEM picture taken from material which had been aged at 140°C. for 500 hours, Figure 3, contains three sets of plate-like precipitates viewed edge-on in the micrograph. The corresponding electron diffraction pattern (not shown) indicated that the orientation of the foil was such that the electron beam was parallel to [110], from which it was deduced that the edge-on precipitates were lying on {100} and {111} planes of the aluminium lattice. Furthermore, it was concluded that two types of precipitate were present. The first was identified as θ' phase (CuAl_2), a tetragonal structure with $a_0 = 0.404$ nm and $c_0 = 0.580$ nm [5]; these were the precipitates which lay on the {100} planes. The precipitates lying on the {111} planes were concluded to be Ω phase, reported as an orthorhombic structure with $a_0 = 0.496$ nm, $b = 0.859$ nm and $c_0 = 0.848$ nm [6]. The total volume fraction of precipitate was ~ 0.05, with approximately three times as much Ω phase present in the specimen as θ' phase.

3.2 Saffil fibre composite

The as-cast composite showed extensive cracking through its centre. Fibre distribution was not uniform, with large areas (up to several 10s of μm in extent) of unreinforced matrix. Grain-boundary particles were in evidence of similar composition to those in the unreinforced alloy (with copper, aluminium, iron and manganese). After solution-treatment, there was less grain-boundary phase in the material. Furthermore, magnesium could not be detected in the matrix (EPMA detection sensitivity ~ 0.05 wt.%).

Figure 4 shows the ageing response of the composite at 140°C. Hardness values in the early stages of ageing were little different from that of unreinforced material, but the maximum hardness of ~150 HV was reached in less time, ~200 hours instead of ~500 hours. Figure 5 is an optical micrograph taken from peak-hardness material near the edge of the fibre-reinforced region. This shows extensive development of two types of second phase. One phase (size ~ 10 μm) was fairly equiaxed in shape and consisted of aluminium and copper in amounts which equated with the intermetallic CuAl_2 ; a trace (~ 0.5 wt.%) of iron was also present. The other type of particle was elongated (~ 30 μm) and contained ~ 67 wt.% aluminium, ~ 28 wt.% copper, ~ 5 wt.% iron and ~1 wt.% manganese, a composition which is similar to that recorded for the less soluble phase in unreinforced material. These two types of intermetallic phase were not, however, usually found in central regions of the composite.

A TEM picture from the peak-hardness material is illustrated in Figure 6a, taken with the electron beam along [100]. Two perpendicular sets of edge-on precipitates are present, which were identified from the corresponding electron diffraction pattern as θ' phase lying on {100} planes of the aluminium lattice. No evidence of Ω phase was found in this specimen. Figure 6b shows a typical distribution of dislocations in the aluminium matrix.

3.3. TiB_2 particulate composite

Figure 7 is an optical micrograph of as-received material showing a non-uniform dispersion of

small particles, $< 2\mu\text{m}$ in size. Figure 8a, taken in the SEM using back-scattered electron imaging, reveals a small amount of porosity as well as clusters of particulate material. EPMA data are given in Figures 8b and 8c as x-ray maps illustrating the distribution of titanium and boron respectively, quantitative measurements identifying the particulates as titanium boride. Figure 7 shows, in addition, larger (up to $10\mu\text{m}$) particles which contained many elements, typically ~ 50 wt.% aluminium, ~ 16 wt.% titanium and manganese, ~ 7 wt.% silicon and iron, and ~ 5 wt.% copper. These, clearly, were very different from the intermetallic phases found in other materials investigated in this study.

Hardness measurements as a function of ageing time at 140°C . are plotted in Figure 9. It may be seen that in the solution-treated condition the hardness is significantly greater than the other two materials in the same condition, $\sim 120\text{HV}$ compared with $\sim 100\text{HV}$. It was noted also that the value varied a great deal, depending upon the position of the indenter with respect to the clusters of particulate. The hardness increased to $\sim 150\text{HV}$ during the first few hours treatment to reach a maximum value after 200 hours which approached 180HV , again higher than corresponding values for the other two materials. There was an indication that the complex intermetallics had slightly increased in size, in some cases up to $20\mu\text{m}$, but the boride dispersion was unaffected.

Figure 10a, a TEM micrograph taken from material in the peak-hardness condition, contains an electron-opaque particle some $1\mu\text{m}$ or so in size which EDS showed contained titanium; the corresponding SAD pattern confirmed the particle as being TiB_2 , a hexagonal structure with $a_0 = 0.303\text{ nm}$ and $c_0 = 0.323\text{ nm}$. Figure 10b reveals fairly large (up to $1\mu\text{m}$ in size) plate-like precipitates, which electron diffraction showed were θ' phase lying on $\{100\}$ planes of the aluminium lattice. No evidence of Ω phase was found.

4. DISCUSSION

The presence of Saffil fibre reinforcement in a composite based upon aluminium-copper-magnesium-silver alloy has been shown to have marked effects upon the development of precipitates within the matrix. The first noticeable feature was that the hardness maximum was reached in much less time than for unreinforced alloy, ~ 200 hours compared with ~ 500 hours respectively, although the hardness value achieved ($\sim 150\text{ HV}$) was little changed. Furthermore, a study of the microstructure revealed a difference in the precipitation mode, fairly large precipitates of θ' having formed in the composite but not the Ω -precipitation mode usually associated with alloy formulations of this type. It should, however, be noted that the averaged matrix magnesium content in the composite was less than $0.05\text{ wt.}\%$, the minimum level detectable by our EPMA technique, whereas it is well known that the magnesium level is critical as regards the formation of Ω phase. Indeed, most reports discussing its formation involve alloys containing between 0.5% and 1.0% magnesium [4]. Thus the first conclusion to be drawn from the results is that the low level of magnesium was insufficient to promote the formation of Ω precipitates, from which it follows that the θ -precipitation sequence would be the favoured mode. The likelihood, although it needs verification, is that the low level of magnesium is a consequence of some of it having reacted with the alumina fibres, as has been noted previously [8] in such composites.

The second feature of note was that the θ' precipitates in the Saffil-reinforced composite were much fewer in number and somewhat larger, up to 500nm in length, than the precipitates normally associated with the peak-hardness condition in unreinforced aluminium-copper alloys or in the quaternary system investigated here. These observations underline clearly the important part played by dislocations created by thermal stresses upon cooling the composite. In this respect,

the dislocation density recorded in the composite matrix (see Figure 6b) was in excess of $3 \times 10^7 \text{mm}^{-2}$, a value similar to that reported in earlier work on alumina fibre reinforced aluminium alloy [8] manufactured using the LMI method. Such densities typify small strains of less than 0.5% and show a measure of agreement with the contraction strain of $\sim 0.8\%$ calculated using thermal expansion coefficients of $23 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ and $8 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ for aluminium and alumina respectively. Thus suitable precipitate nucleation sites are provided by the dislocations such that θ' precipitates can form directly on them and thereby by-pass the early stages of the θ -precipitation sequence, that is the formation of GP zones or θ'' phase. Bearing in mind the large number of dislocations available as nucleation sites in the composite, it is somewhat surprising to find a somewhat coarse precipitate structure, size ~ 100 to 250nm , present at this stage of the ageing reaction. This leads to the conclusion that the dislocations have played a second role in the precipitation process and have enhanced the diffusion of solute and promoted the rate of growth of precipitate. Despite, however, the precipitate structure being not optimised for the maximum hardening response, the increase of some 50 HV over the solution-treated condition which was achieved in this composite was not very different from the $\sim 50 \text{HV}$ produced in the absence of reinforcement. These observations would suggest, therefore, that the mechanism of matrix hardening in metal matrix composites is fairly complex, with precipitates, dislocations and reinforcements all contributing to the process.

The composite reinforced with TiB_2 particulate also showed a response to the ageing treatment and, as with the Saffil-reinforced composite, only the θ' phase was formed. Indeed in this material the matrix composition would dictate that only θ' phase would be produced upon ageing, and the results seem to confirm this, although a recent report [9] indicated that an Ω -type structure could be formed in the absence of silver. Again the precipitates were relatively large and the hardening increment was fairly modest, the raised level of the hardness curve (compare Figure 9 with Figure 4) being attributable to the dispersion of titanium borides. Unfortunately this dispersion is seen to be far from optimised in the composite.

Before concluding, it must be said that some doubt remains regarding the efficacy of the homogenising treatment. The fact that after solution treatment a significant amount of intermetallic phase was still present, particularly at grain boundaries, implies that some of the elements required for the hardening process were not then available. This factor may also have contributed to the failure to develop Ω precipitates in Saffil-reinforced composite during subsequent ageing. As a final point, it should be noted that the segregation of intermetallic second phases to regions near the edge of the infiltrated fibres would suggest that by the time the melt had reached regions deeper within the fibre preform, the alloy was no longer able to sustain the required precipitation reaction because of depletion of the elements involved, although further work is needed to confirm this.

References

1. MingYang and Scott, V.D., Interface and Fracture of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Al-7wt.% Si Alloy, *J. Mat. Sci.*, **26**, (1991), pp. 1609-1617.
2. Christman, T., Suresh, S., Microstructural Development in an Aluminium Alloy-SiC Whisker Composite, *Acta Metall.*, **36**, (1988), pp. 1691-1704.
3. Prangnell, P.B. and Stobbs, W.M., The Effect of SiC Particulate Reinforcement on the Ageing Behaviour of Aluminium Based Matrix Alloys, *ICCM7*, eds. Wu Yunshu, Gu Zhenlong and Wu Renjie, (International Academic Publishers: Beijing)1989, pp. 573-578.

4. Taylor, J.A., Parker, B.A. and Polmear, I.J., Precipitation in Al-Cu-Mg-Ag Casting Alloy, *Met. Sci.*, **13**, (1978), pp. 478-482.
5. Scott, V.D., Kerry, S. and Trumper, R.L., Nucleation and Growth of Precipitates in Al-Cu-Mg-Ag Alloys, *Mat. Sci. and Technol.*, **3**, (1987), pp. 827-835.
6. Knowles, K.M. and Stobbs, W.M., The structure of $\{111\}$ Age Hardening Precipitates in Al-Cu-Mg-Ag Alloys, *Acta Crystall.*, **B44** (1988), pp. 207-227.
7. Muddle, B.C. and Polmear, I.J., The Precipitate Ω Phase in Al-Cu-Mg-Ag Alloys, *Acta Metall.*, **37** (1989), pp. 777-789.
8. Ming Yang and Scott, V.D., Microstructural Studies of Aluminium-Silicon Alloy Reinforced with Alumina Fibres, *J. Mat. Sci.*, **26**, (1991), pp. 2245-2254.
9. Fonda, R.W., Cassada, W.A. and Shiflet, G.J., Accommodation of the Misfit Strain Surrounding $\{111\}$ Precipitates (Ω) in Al-Cu-Mg-(Ag), *Acta Metall. Mater.*, **40**, (1992), pp. 2539-2546.

Figure 1 - Unreinforced alloy after solution-treatment (OM).

Figure 2 - Variation of Vickers hardness with ageing time at 140°C for unreinforced alloy.

Figure 3 - Micrograph of unreinforced alloy in peak hardness condition; $[110]$ foil (TEM).

Figure 4 - Variation of Vickers hardness with ageing time at 140°C for Saffil fibre-reinforced composite.

Figure 5 - Region of composite near edge of fibre reinforcement (OM).

Figure 6a - Micrograph of fibre-reinforced composite in peak hardness condition; [100] foil (TEM).

Figure 6b - Dislocation distribution in peak hardness sample of fibre-reinforced composite (TEM).

Figure 7 - As-cast TiB₂ particulate-reinforced composite (OM).

Figure 8 - as-cast particulate-reinforced composite: (a) - Backscattered electron image (SEM). (b) - X-ray map for titanium (EPMA). (c) - X-ray map for boron (EPMA).

Figure 9 - Variation of Vickers hardness with ageing time at 140°C for TiB_2 particulate-reinforced composite.

Figure 10 - TEM micrographs of particulate-reinforced composite in peak hardness condition:

- (a) TiB_2 particle (darker region)
- (b) precipitates on $\{100\}$ planes of aluminium lattice.